

A relict new species of *Circulus* (Truncatelloidea: Vitrinellidae) from a circalittoral bottom off Alboran Island

Una nueva especie relictada de *Circulus* (Truncatelloidea: Vitrinellidae) de un fondo circalitoral de la Isla de Alborán

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urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:4C8787C9-7010-422A-837F-F3B977BC2917

Recibido el 16-V-2024. Aceptado el 6-VI-2024

ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865 collected alive from a deep circalittoral bottom of biogenic gravel off Alboran Island, is described. The new species is compared with similar species previously known from the west coast of Africa, Caribbean and neighboring areas and the Mediterranean Sea and with the fossil species *Circulus miotaurinensis*. The role of the Alboran Sea as refuge for relict faunal elements is highlighted.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865 recolectada viva en un fondo circalitoral profundo de grava biogénica próximo a la Isla de Alborán. La nueva especie se compara con especies similares previamente conocidas de la costa occidental de África, Caribe y áreas próximas y del Mar Mediterráneo, así como con la especie fósil *Circulus miotaurinensis*. Se pone de manifiesto el papel del Mar de Alborán como refugio para especies relictadas.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Especie relictada, Vitrinellidae, Isla de Alborán.

KEY WORDS: Relict species, Vitrinellidae, Alboran Island.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865 has been recently studied by several authors. RUBIO, FERNANDEZ-GARCÉS & ROLÁN (2011) studied the species of the Caribbean and neighbouring areas; OLIVER & ROLÁN (2011) the species in the eastern Atlantic and RUBIO & ROLÁN (2022) those of the Indo-Pacific.

There are currently twelve accepted recent species of *Circulus* in the Atlantic

Ocean, four from the east coast of USA and the Caribbean: *Circulus liratus* (A.E. Verrill, 1882), *C. texanus* (Moore, 1965), *C. semisculptus* (Olsson & McGinty, 1958) and *C. orbigny* (P. Fischer, 1857); and another eight from the eastern Atlantic: *C. striatus* (Philippi, 1836), *C. smithi* Bush, 1897, *C. congoensis* (Thiele, 1925), *C. senegalensis* Adam & Knudsen, 1969, *C. pseudopraecedens* Adams & Knudsen,

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1969, *C. stephani* Rolán & Ryall, 2002, *C. ryalli* Oliver & Rolán, 2011 and *C. microsculpturatus* Oliver & Rolán, 2011.

Here we report on an unusually large specimen collected alive in the Alboran Sea, which is described as new species and compared to the Recent and fossil species of the Atlanto-Mediterranean area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimen studied was collected during the LIFE+ INDEMARES Alborán project (2011-2013). Ten samples (Fig. 1) were taken with the beam trawl gear ("bou de vara") in the extensive deep gravel bottoms that are found between 80 and 200 m on the platform surrounding the Alboran Island, formed by biogenic calcareous remains (bioclasts) (GOFAS ET AL., 2014b).

This sampling revealed a high richness of invertebrate species. In the case of molluscs, the specific richness of the samples was between 24 and 55 species in standard samples of ca. 3 kg of sediment,

while the abundances were between moderate and high (between 154 and 846 individuals per sample, in total over 2000). In addition to the standard samples of 3 kg, a large amount of dried sediment was sorted thoroughly for hauls BV21 (0.8 kg < 1 mm; 0.8 kg 1-3 mm; 9.0 kg 3-5 mm; 3.6 kg > 5 mm), BV33 (1.0 kg < 1 mm; 8.2 kg 1-3 mm; 12.0 kg 3-5 mm; 6.7 kg > 5 mm) and BV35 (2.3 kg < 1 mm; 10.3 kg 1-3 mm; 13.4 kg 3-5 mm; 6.1 kg > 5 mm). This extended sampling yielded, in BV21, nearly 1000 specimens belonging to 80 species (vs. 26 in , the standard sample), among which that one described herein.

The sampling site is part of the Site of Community Importance "Alboran" ES6110015, established in July 2006 but not yet declared as SAC due to the competency conflict between national and regional governments for this area.

Abbreviations

MNCN: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid.

NHMW: Natural History Museum, Vienna.

spm: specimen with soft parts.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily TRUNCATELLOIDEA Gray, 1840

Family VITRINELLIDAE Bush, 1897

Genus *Circulus* Jeffreys, 1865

Type species by monotypy: *Delphinula duminyi* Requier, 1848 accepted as *Circulus striatus* (Philippi, 1836). Recent, Europe.

Circulus aemilii n. sp. (Fig. 2)

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Type material: Spain. *Holotype*: • 1 spm (Fig. 2); Alboran platform; 36°00.29'N, 02°55.57'W-36°00.40'N, 02°55.32'W; 93-101 m; 24 Sept. 2011; INDEMARES Alboran BV21; deep bioclastic gravel; MNCN 15.05/200551.

Type locality: Alboran platform; 36°00.29'N, 02°55.57'W-36°00.40'N, 02°55.32'W; 93-101 m.

Etymology: The specific name is dedicated to our colleague Emilio Rolán, as a tribute to his involvement in the study of this and many other genera of micromolluscs.

Description: Shell small (< 5.0 mm in diameter), discoidal, depressed-turbini-form, formed by 4 ¾ whorls, keeled and widely umbilicate.

The protoconch slightly protrudes over the teleoconch, has 2 ¼ whorls, with a size of about 490 µm in diameter and two distinct phases; apparently it is

Figure 1. Location of samples collected during the INDEMARES Alboran cruise, using the beam trawl on deep bioclastic gravels (adapted from GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2014b). The new species was obtained in haul BV21.

Figura 1. Localización de muestras recogidas durante la campaña INDEMARES Alborán, utilizando el bou de vara sobre gravas bioclásticas profundas (adaptado de GOFAS ET AL., 2014b). La especie nueva se obtuvo en el lance BV21.

totally smooth; the transition to the teleoconch is clear by the change of the sculpture (Fig. 2B).

The teleoconch has 2 ½ whorls and its outline is convex apically and strongly keeled peripherally and basally. Ornamentation formed by keels, spiral cords and growth lines. Since its beginning, the entire surface of the teleoconch is covered by spiral cords; 5-6 rounded spiral cords can be seen at beginning of the teleoconch.

There are two carinae (peripheral and basal), triangular in cross section; both carinae protrudes as keels; the peripheral keel is located in the middle of the periphery and the basal keel, the most protruding, extends abapically. There is no cord or carina that delimits the umbilicus.

The spiral cords are narrower than interspaces and rounded in cross section; 9-10 cords can be seen between the suture and the peripheral keel; 4 cords between the peripheral keel and

the basal keel and other 18-20 cords between the basal keel and inside the umbilicus. The interspaces are concave and of distinct size.

Marked sinuous growth lines can be seen all over the surface of the teleoconch and mainly inside the umbilicus.

Umbilicus very wide and deep, allowing to see the inner whorls; the wall is very convex and inside there are 10-12 fine spiral cords crossed by marked growth lines (Fig. 2C).

Aperture rounded, very prosocline (Fig. 2D). Inner lip with the parietal area covered by a callous layer and the columella arched and reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip with a bevelled edge, internally angled by the keels; subsutural an upper peripheral area projected outward.

Dimensions: the holotype measures 4.50 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Only known from the holotype, living in circalittoral biogenic gravel at 93-101 m deep.

Figure 2. *Circulus aemilii* n. sp. Holotype (MNCN 15.05/200551). Indemares Alboran, Stn BV21, 93-101 m, deep biogenic gravel (diameter 4.5 mm). A: apical view; B: detail of the apex (the arrow indicates the transition to the teleoconch); C: umbilical view; D: lateral view.

Figure 2. *Circulus aemilii* n. sp. Holotipo (MNCN 15.05/200551), Indemares Alborán, Stn BV21, 93-101 m, cascajo biogénico profundo (diámetro 4,5 mm). A: vista apical; B: detalle del ápice (la flecha indica la transición a la teloconcha); C: vista umbilical; D: vista lateral.

Distribution: only known from Alboran Island.

Remarks: *Circulus aemilii* n. sp. is characterized by its large size, compared to other Recent species of the genus; for having 2 keels (peripheral and basal) of which the basal keel is the most prominent, the teleoconch totally covered by spiral cords and upper peripheral area projected outward and by lacking a thick periumbilical cord delimiting the umbilicus.

The fossil species *Circulus miotaurinensis* (Sacco, 1896) (Fig. 3) is certainly the most similar, and probable ancestor. The type specimens of *Adeorbis miotaurinensis* from Miocene strata of “Colli Torinesi” (hills around Turin) were illustrated by FERRERO-MORTARA ET AL. (1984: 275, pl. 50 fig. 4), as well as the type of var. *plioastensis* (pl. 50 fig. 6)

from the Pliocene of “Colli Astesi” (hills around Asti). *Circulus miotaurinensis* was reported from the Early Pliocene of Estepona, Southern Spain (LANDAU, MARQUET & GRIGIS, 2004: 58, pl. 13, fig. 2; LANDAU & MULDER, 2020: 34, fig. 16).

Both *Circulus miotaurinensis* and its variety differ from *C. aemilii* by having the 1.5 first teleoconch whorls smooth (completely covered by spiral cords in *C. aemilii*) and last whorl with 10-15 spiral cords between the suture and the peripheral keel, while the space between keels and the space between the basal keel and the umbilicus lack spiral cords (*C. aemilii* has 31-34 spiral cords between the suture and the umbilicus). Interestingly, the Pliocene specimen of *C. miotaurinensis* illustrated by LANDAU & MULDER (2020; here reproduced in Fig. 3, as *C. cf. miotaurinensis*)

Figure 3. *Circulus* cf. *miotaurinensis* (Sacco, 1896) (NHMW 2019/0167/0052), Pliocene fossil from El Lobillo, Estepona (diameter 8.4 mm). A: apical view; B: umbilical view; C: lateral view. Reproduced from LANDAU & MULDER (2020: fig. 16), with permission.

Figure 3. *Circulus* cf. *miotaurinensis* (Sacco, 1896) (NHMW 2019/0167/0052), fósil del Plioceno de El Lobillo, Estepona (diámetro 8,4 mm). A: vista apical; B: vista umbilical; C: vista lateral. Reproducido de LANDAU & MULDER (2020: fig. 16), con permiso.

does have a spiral striation on the apical part of the early whorls, but still differs from *C. aemilii* n. sp. in completely lacking spiral sculpture between the abapical keel and the umbilicus. *Circulus miotaurinensis* reaches a much larger size (a little more than 13 mm according to LANDAU ET AL., 2004, vs. 4.5 mm) than the Alboran specimen, and some specimens have a weak periumbilical cord.

Otherwise, *C. aemilii* is similar in general appearance to *Circulus smithi* Bush, 1897 recorded from Ouidah, Benin (type locality), from Libreville, Gabon (ADAM & KNUDSEN, 1969: 16-18, fig. 8) and from Nouakchott, Mauritania (OLIVER & ROLÁN, 2011: figs. 7A-D), but differs from this by its larger size (4.5 mm vs 2.7 mm); by having a greater number of cords between the suture and the peripheral cord (9-10 vs 6-7) and between the basal keel and inside the umbilicus (18-20 vs 10-12); by lacking

the cord delimiting the umbilicus and by having subsutural and upper peripheral areas projected outward.

The remaining species from the eastern Atlantic and Caribbean are smaller, their size ranges between 2 - 3.5 mm, while the new species measures 4.5 mm. *Circulus striatus*, type species of the genus, differs in having only spiral cords, not forming keels although some specimens appear with some cords more developed as carinae/keels, placed in subsutural, peripheral and basal positions. *Circulus orbigny*, *C. semisculptus*, *C. liratus*, *C. congoensis* and *C. senegalensis* differ by completely lacking keels. *Circulus pseudopraecedens* and *C. ryalli* differs in having only the peripheral keel and *Circulus texanus* only the basal keel. *Circulus stephani* and *C. microsculpturatus* differs by having three keels (upper or subsutural, peripheral and basal).

DISCUSSION

This unusual occurrence suggests a relict distribution, compared to that of the probable ancestor *C. miotaurinensis* distributed across the entire Western Mediterranean. This geographical restriction is not likely to be an artefact, taking into account the relatively large size and the considerable effort on sampling and sorting the same depth interval along the coasts of continental Spain and Italy. A comparable case can be seen with the occurrence of *Graphis pruinosa* Gofas & Rueda, 2014 which is only known living on Djibouti Banks in the Alboran Sea (GOFAS ET AL., 2014a) but was recently recorded from the Pliocene of Estepona, along the mainland shore (LANDAU & MICALI, 2021). In any case, this and other occurrences of rare

species support the considerable conservation interest of those deep bioclastic gravels topping the submarine elevations of the Alboran Sea.

This finding highlights the role of the Alboran Sea area as a haven for relict faunal elements. LANDAU ET AL. (2004: 87) have noted that during the Pliocene, the Estepona basin harboured relict faunal elements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We warmly thank Bernard Landau for constructive comments on the draft of this manuscript, and for permission to reproduce his pictures of the fossil *Circulus miotaurinensis*.

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